

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

FLAGSHIP PROJECT GRIP

SPOKE N 2 – Title GREEN TECHNOLOGIES AND SUSTAINABLE INDUSTRIES

DELIVERABLE D5.2.2

DELIVERABLE D5.2.3

DELIVERABLE D5.2.4

Version history

No.	Date	Details	Author(s)
1	10/06/2025		Silvia Fraterrigo Garofalo Debora Fino

This document is part of the project NODES which has received funding from the MUR – Missione 4, Componente 2, Investimento 1.5 – Creazione e rafforzamento di “Ecosistemi dell’innovazione”, costruzione di “leader territoriali di R&S” – del PNRR with grant agreement no. ECS00000036

Contents

NODES Nord Ovest Digitale E Sostenibile	1
<i>VERSION HISTORY</i>	1
GLOSSARY	4
A) MAIN OBJECTIVES ACHIEVED	5
B) RESEARCH MODULE N° 5	5
CO ₂ CAPTURE AND CONVERSION PLATFORM: BIOCHEMICAL, CHEMO-CATALYTIC AND ELECTROCHEMICAL	5
CONVERSION PROCESSES	5
LIST OF DELIVERABLES.....	6
<i>Table - List of Deliverables</i>	6
LIST OF MILESTONES	7
<i>Table - List of Project Milestones</i>	7
C) GENERAL DESCRIPTION OF THE DELIVERABLE D5.2.2	8
D) DELIVERABLE D5.2.2	8
E) REFERENCES	11
F) GENERAL DESCRIPTION OF THE DELIVERABLE D5.2.3	12
G) DELIVERABLE D5.2.3	12
H) REFERENCES	13
I) GENERAL DESCRIPTION OF THE DELIVERABLE D5.2.4	14
J) DELIVERABLE D5.2.4	14

K)	REFERENCES	21
L)	OTHER ACTIVITIES.....	21
M)	DESCRIPTION OF TASK 5.2.5 CARBON MINERALIZATION.	21
N)	TASK 5.2.5 CARBON MINERALIZATION.	22

Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to “Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”
NODES’ Research and innovation program	NODES’ Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES’ Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES’ Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke’s ecosystem. It refers to “Spoke” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke’s ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke’ leadership and management. It refers to “soggetti affiliati” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”.
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES’ Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

A) Main objectives achieved

The main objectives of this RM are the definition and selection of the technological solutions available to be tested at the industrial level for CO₂ capture and conversion and the expected results from the activities foreseen in this RM will lead, through a comparison between the different technologies at the level of applied research, to the definition of the best technologies available in this sector.

During this first 10 month of project the task 5.1 has been completed (more details from page 8 to page 22) and in particular the main results achieved are:

- The existing literature was examined to assess the current state of the art in CO₂ capture materials.
- A CO₂ capture material was chosen to synthesize, characterize and test.
- The existing literature was examined to assess the current state of the art in CO₂ conversion through chemical, photochemical, electrochemical, and biochemical processes.
- The technologies and materials to be tested for the chemical, photochemical, electrochemical, and biochemical conversion of CO₂ into high-value-added molecules have been selected.
- The typical composition of gas emissions from a power plant was determined to select the gaseous mixtures for conducting CO₂ capture and conversion tests..
- Milestone 5.1 has been achieved (more details at page 24).

B) Research Module n° 5

CO₂ capture and conversion platform: biochemical, chemo-catalytic and electrochemical conversion processes

RM5 will deal with Carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions. CO₂ is one of the main responsible of the rapid rise in global temperature. The RM5 plans to identify a suitable technology for the capture and conversion of CO₂ for industrial application in a steady state. Mineral capture of CO₂ from industrial/engines emissions will be applied and evaluated in synergy with the other carbon capture methods with a view to providing a diverse portfolio of solutions to the carbon dioxide rise in the atmosphere. Carbon capture and storage will complete the previous approaches to the reduction of the impact of urban and industrial waste by acting on the gaseous waste from

anthropic activities. The RM5 also aims to develop a suitable technology for the subsequent conversion of trapped CO₂ for the synthesis of methanol and other high-value molecules through multiple synthetic bio-chemical, chemical and electrochemical strategies. The processes will be optimized first on a laboratory scale and subsequently validated on a pilot scale.

List of Deliverables

Table - List of Deliverables

N°	OUTPUTS/DELIVERABLE NAME	TYPE *	SHORT DESCRIPTION	LEAD PARTICIPANT	DISSEMINATION LEVEL **	DUE DATE
5.1	Data acquisition and material characterization	R	Collection of data, Characterization of the composition of gases at the emittee for the identification of the specifications required for CO ₂ capture and conversion, selection of the experimental set-ups.	POLITO	PU	10
5.2.1	Development and optimization of	R	Synthesis, characterization and	POLITO-UNITO	PU	20

	materials and systems for CO ₂ capture.		tests on adsorption materials			
5.2.2	CO ₂ Conversion by thermochemistry.	R	Tests, evaluation of material conversion capacity and products characterization	POLITO	PU	30
5.2.3	CO ₂ Conversion by electrochemistry	R	Tests, evaluation of material conversion capacity and product characterization	POLITO	PU	30
5.2.4	Biochemical conversion of CO ₂	R	Optimization of the growth process and products characterization	POLITO	PU	30
5.3	Products application	R	Investigation of market trends and application of products	POLITO	PU	32
5.4	Environmental constraints	R	Comparison between the three processes of CO ₂ being equal from an environmental sustainability point of view	POLITO	PU	32

List of Milestones

Table - List of Project Milestones

MILESTONE NUMBER	MILESTONE NAME	RELATED WORK MODULES	DUE DATE (MONTH)	MEANS OF VERIFICATION
M5.1	CO ₂ capture and conversion materials	5	10	At least one material to be tested for each conversion process and also microorganism for the biochemical

				process will be selected.
M5.2	CO ₂ capture and conversion processes	5	32	The best process will be identified among those investigated from a technical, economic and environmental point of view.

C) General description of the Deliverable D5.2.2

CO₂ Conversion by thermochemistry

In this task, carbon dioxide (CO₂) will undergo conversion into methanol and other high-value molecules through processes involving elevated pressure and/or temperature. The Politecnico di Torino (Polito) will conduct a comprehensive study to determine the optimal temperature and pressure conditions, as well as the most effective catalyst composition, to maximize CO₂ conversion efficiency. The research will focus on evaluating the catalytic activity, long-term stability, and product quality using advanced chromatographic and spectroscopic analytical techniques. The selection of the catalyst will be based on key performance criteria, including conversion efficiency, operational feasibility, and durability under laboratory conditions. Once the optimal catalyst and process parameters are identified, the most promising solution may be further validated through larger-scale testing.

D) Deliverable D5.2.2

CO₂ Conversion by thermochemistry

The rising levels of atmospheric CO₂ demand sustainable technologies for carbon capture and conversion. Power-to-gas (PtG) systems offer a promising solution for both carbon mitigation and energy storage by converting CO₂ into methane using green H₂. Ru-based systems may be considered more suitable when designing an ideal catalyst for PtG applications. Conversely to the traditional direct CO₂ methanation, a cyclic process could enhance the operational and energy efficiency of the process. This configuration allows the reduction of system costs and complexity by more effectively utilising the heat generated from the exothermic reaction to facilitate CO₂ desorption. In addition to contributing to decreasing CO₂ emissions, this process can be effectively coupled with discontinuous renewable hydrogen sources for sustainable methane production. Among the numerous adsorbents examined in the literature, magnesium

oxide (MgO) is a promising candidate for CO₂ capture due to its surface basicity and ability to generate oxygen vacancies, enhancing CO₂ adsorption. Compared to other metal oxide adsorbents, such as those based on lithium and calcium, MgO offers the advantage of a lower regeneration temperature (< 500 °C). It is particularly effective in intermediate temperature ranges (200–400 °C) and has a high theoretical CO₂ uptake capacity of 24.8 mmol/g. However, pure MgO faces challenges despite its potential, including low surface area, slow adsorption kinetics, and thermal stability issues during high-temperature desorption, which may lead to sintering and reduced efficiency. In this context, Mg-based hydrotalcite (HT) materials (also known as layered double hydroxides, LDHs) have gained increasing attention as CO₂ adsorbents and precursors for catalysts for methanation reaction, as it is possible to obtain materials with large metal surface area, small metal particle size, excellent thermal stability and uniform distribution of active sites. Ru-based hydrotalcite-derived materials for CO₂ adsorption and methanation cycles is still scarce, to the best of the authors' knowledge.

This part of the project investigated the use of Ru-based catalysts supported on Mg-Al oxides (MgAl) and MgO as dual-function materials (DFMs) for cyclic CO₂ adsorption and methanation under realistic dry and wet conditions at atmospheric pressure.

Supports based on MgO and MgAl (from calcined hydrotalcite) were prepared. A K-doped sample (K/MgAl) was also synthesized to increase the surface basicity and enhance adsorption capacity. Catalysts were synthesized via incipient wetness impregnation using ruthenium nitrosyl nitrate to achieve a nominal Ru loading of 2 wt%. The samples were then dried, calcined, and reduced under hydrogen to generate the active metal phase.

The catalysts were extensively characterized using several characterization techniques:

ICP-MS, XRD, N₂ physisorption, FESEM/EDX: to determine elemental composition, crystallinity, surface area and morphology, respectively.

CO₂-TPD and H₂-TPR: to evaluate the surface basicity, the CO₂ adsorption capacity, the reducibility of the samples and the H₂ uptake.

Operando FTIR spectroscopy: to identify surface intermediates during CO₂ capture and methanation, that could help to identify the reaction mechanism.

Catalytic tests involved cyclic experiments simulating industrial conditions: CO₂ was adsorbed (with or without moisture), followed by methanation with hydrogen at 250 - 320 °C.

Main results obtained from this work are the following:

Ru/MgAl outperformed Ru/MgO in both adsorption and methanation due to its higher surface area, finer dispersion of active sites and better distribution of Ru.

Doping with K₂CO₃ (Ru-K/MgAl) further increased CO₂ capture, but it slowed the kinetics due to more stable carbonates and lower surface area.

Operando FTIR confirmed different reaction pathways and intermediates for Ru/MgAl and Ru-K/MgAl, explaining the different reaction pathways.

Fig. 1. Representative evolution of the operando FTIR spectra collected during the CO₂ capture/reduction cycle with the catalysts Ru/MgAl

All catalysts showed high selectivity to methane and good cyclic stability, with Ru/MgAl achieving CH₄ yields up to 220 μmol/g under wet conditions. Reaction temperature and moisture influenced both adsorption and CH₄ production. In particular, moisture enhanced the CO₂ uptake and increased the CH₄ selectivity, reducing CO production.

The project demonstrated that Ru/MgAl catalysts are effective DFMs for CO₂ capture and methanation, with excellent cyclic stability and potential for integration into PtG systems. The combination of structural optimization and operando analysis provides valuable insight for future development of efficient CO₂-to-CH₄ conversion technologies.

Fig.2. Schematic representation of the reaction network hypothesised from the spectroscopic outcomes of time-resolved operando FTIR measurements for A) Ru/MgAl

E) References

1. Porta, R. Matarrese, C.G. Visconti, L. Castoldi, L. Lietti, Storage material effects on the performance of Ru-based CO₂ capture and methanation dual functioning materials, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* 60 (2021) 6706–6718, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.iecr.0c05898>.
2. S. Cimino, R. Russo, L. Lisi, Insights into the cyclic CO₂ capture and catalytic methanation over highly performing Li-Ru/Al₂O₃ dual function materials, *Chem. Eng. J.* 428 (2022) 131275, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2021.131275>.
3. Rizzetto, M. Piumetti, R. Pirone, E. Sartoretti, S. Bensaid, Study of ceriacomposite materials for high-temperature CO₂ capture and their ruthenium functionalization for methane production, *Catal. Today* 429 (2024) 114478, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cattod.2023.114478>.
4. P. Melo Bravo, D.P. Debecker, Combining CO₂ capture and catalytic conversion to methane, *Waste Dispos Sustain. Energy* 1 (2019) 53–65, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42768-019-00004-0>.
5. Y. Guo, C. Tan, P. Wang, J. Sun, W. Li, C. Zhao, P. Lu, Magnesium-based basic mixtures derived from earth-abundant natural minerals for CO₂ capture in simulated flue gas, *Fuel* 243 (2019) 298–305, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuel.2019.01.108>.
6. V. Hiremath, H.J. Kwon, I. Jung, S. Kwon, S.H. Kwon, S.G. Lee, H.C. Lee, J.G. Seo, Mg-ion inversion in MgO@MgO/Al₂O₃ oxides: the origin of basic sites, *ChemSusChem* 12 (2019) 2810–2818, <https://doi.org/10.1002/cssc.201900072>.
7. W. Gao, T. Zhou, Y. Gao, B. Louis, D. O'Hare, Q. Wang, Molten salts-modified MgO-based adsorbents for intermediate-temperature CO₂ capture: a review, *Journal of Energy Chemistry* 26 (2017) 830–838, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jechem.2017.06.005>.
8. P. Li, R. Chen, Y. Lin, W. Li, General approach to facile synthesis of MgO-based porous ultrathin nanosheets enabling high-efficiency CO₂ capture, *Chem. Eng. J.* 404 (2021) 126459, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2020.126459>.
9. S. Abate, K. Barbera, E. Giglio, F. Deorsola, S. Bensaid, S. Perathoner, R. Pirone, G. Centi, Synthesis, characterization, and activity pattern of Ni–Al hydrotalcite catalysts in CO₂ methanation, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* 55 (2016) 8299–8308, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.iecr.6b01581>.
10. P. Marocco, E.A. Morosanu, E. Giglio, D. Ferrero, C. Mebrahtu, A. Lanzini, S. Abate, S. Bensaid, S. Perathoner, M. Santarelli, R. Pirone, G. Centi, CO₂ methanation over Ni/Al hydrotalcite-derived catalyst: experimental characterization and kinetic study, *Fuel* 225 (2018) 230–242, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuel.2018.03.137>.
11. [10.1016/j.fuel.2018.03.137](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuel.2018.03.137).
12. Rizzetto, E. Sartoretti, M. Piumetti, R. Pirone, S. Bensaid, Novel application of Ru-based catalysts on MgAl oxides alkaline adsorbents for cyclic CO₂ methanation, *Chemical*

Engineering Journal 501 (2024) 157585 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2024.157585>

F) General description of the Deliverable D5.2.3

The research activity of Polito and UniPV will concern the development of new catalysts composed of metal nanoparticles alloyed with other metals. They will be supported on carbonaceous structures, synthesized through scalable techniques Polito. The bulk and surface properties of the catalysts will be studied through chemical-physical, microscopic and spectroscopic characterization techniques. The catalysts will be tested in electrochemical reactor. The role of the various components of the catalyst, for the catalytic activity and their stability (not known in the literature), will be studied through tests in available plants and the reaction products will be analysed through gas and liquid chromatography (micro-GC and HPLC).

G) Deliverable D5.2.3

CO₂ Conversion by electrochemistry

The continuous growth of the global population is driving an ever-increasing energy demand. However, society remains dependent on petroleum-based infrastructure while grappling with the inherent intermittency of renewable energy sources, highlighting the urgent need for innovative solutions. In this context, mitigating ecosystem damage has become a key priority, with the carbon cycle emerging as a focal point of research. Carbon Capture and Sequestration (CCS) technologies, alongside Electrochemical CO₂ Reduction (ECCO₂R), offer a promising approach to transforming CO₂ from a pollutant into a valuable resource. By reducing atmospheric CO₂ levels, this strategy addresses environmental concerns and repurposes CO₂ as a raw material for synthesizing chemicals and fuels. Among electrocatalytic materials, polycrystalline Cu stands out as the only metal capable of producing a variety of hydrocarbons and alcohols. However, its lack of selectivity toward specific product classes remains a significant limitation. In contrast, Copper(I) Oxide Cu₂O has been shown to exhibit superior selectivity for C₂/C₂₊ products, making it a more promising candidate for targeted hydrocarbon production.

The work during the last months focused on the synthesis of Cu₂O nano-catalyst for ECCO₂R with enhanced selectivity toward C₂/C₂₊ products. Moreover, different synthesis routes have been explored, leveraging three distinct capping agents: Polyvinylpyrrolidone 40, Cetrimonium bromide, and Polyvinylpyrrolidone K30, in order to obtain diverse nanoparticle (NP) morphologies. Silver has been added as a source of adsorbed -CO on the catalyst surface. The effect of silver deposition at varying concentrations on the Cu₂O NPs surface has also been investigated. Optimizing NPs morphology generates abundant oxygen vacancies, which increase local charge density, thereby improving CO₂ adsorption and activation. Moreover, the Ag deposition on Cu₂O NPs has enhanced the concentration of *CO on the catalyst surface.

Thermodynamically and kinetically favorable *CO spillover from Ag to Cu sites promotes C–C coupling, improving selectivity toward C₂₊ products. All synthesized NPs have been characterized by specific surface area, crystallite sizes, electrochemical surface area, composition, and morphology. Six powders have been tested as electrocatalysts in a flow-continuous cell with direct gas-phase humidified CO₂ injection at -50 mAcm⁻². The working electrode was a half-membrane Electrode Assembly (half-MEA) with an anionic exchange membrane (FAA3-30). Product selectivity has been analyzed and correlated with the characterization results. The results revealed that the Cu₂O with Ag 1 %mol sample exhibits a significantly higher Faradaic Efficiency (FE) for C₂ and C₂₊ products (34.59% ethylene 12.45% ethanol and 6.30% 1-propanol at -50 mA cm⁻²). This result can be correlated to the highest average crystallite size (43.7 nm), the smallest average pore width (109.8 nm), the highest double-layer capacitance (1.78 μF, indicating superior electrocatalytic activity), and the highest NPs mean diameter (137 nm) with spherical morphology. However, increasing the Ag content beyond 1 %mol appears to negatively impact performance, as evidenced by the sharp decline in FEs observed in Cu₂O with Ag 2%mol. The most promising samples have been deposited on a gas diffusion layer (GDL) with a microporous layer, to enhance CO₂ diffusivity and suppress hydrogen production (HER, the most diffuse CO₂ reduction competitor). However, as the silver amount increases, the decreasing trend in C₂ and C₂₊ selectivity is maintained, highlighting the detrimental effect of excessive Ag deposition. In conclusion, a wide study has been conducted on the possibility of Cu₂O tuneability over C₂₊ production. The promising results can be now used as a starting point for further investigations, in order to obtain a facile tunable catalyst for CO₂ reduction towards a wide range of high-value products.

H) References

- (1) Hernández, S.; Farkhondehfal, M. A.; Sastre, F.; Makkee, M.; Saracco, G.; Russo, N. Syngas Production from Electrochemical Reduction of CO₂: Current Status and Prospective Implementation. *Green Chem.* 2017, 19 (10), 2326–2346. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c7gc00398f>.
- (2) Guzmán, H.; Russo, N.; Hernández, S. CO₂ valorisation towards Alcohols by Cu-Based Electrocatalysts: Challenges and Perspectives. *Green Chem.* 2021, 23 (5), 1896–1920. <https://doi.org/10.1039/d0gc03334k>.
- (3) Guzmán, H.; Zammillo, F.; Roldán, D.; Galletti, C.; Russo, N.; Hernández, S. Investigation of Gas Diffusion Electrode Systems for the Electrochemical CO₂ Conversion. *Catalysts* **2021**, 11 (4). <https://doi.org/10.3390/catal11040482>.
- (4) Guzmán, H.; Roldán, D.; Sacco, A.; Castellino, M.; Fontana, M.; Russo, N.; Hernández, S. CuZnAl-Oxide Nanopyramidal Mesoporous Materials for the Electrocatalytic CO₂ Reduction to Syngas: Tuning of H₂/CO Ratio. *Nanomaterials* **2021**, 11 (11). <https://doi.org/10.3390/nano11113052>.
- (5) Zoli, M.; Roldán, D.; Guzmán, H.; Castellino, M.; Chiodoni, A.; Bejtka, K.; Russo, N.; Hernández,

S. Facile and Scalable Synthesis of Cu₂O-SnO₂ Catalyst for the Photoelectrochemical CO₂ Conversion. *Catal. Today* **2023**, 413–415 (October 2022).
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cattod.2022.12.016>.

I) General description of the Deliverable D5.2.4

This task will be conducted by Polito and Unito who will deal with the selection of microorganisms (including microalgae capable of growing in high CO₂ concentrations, e.g., *B. braunii*) and / or enzymes for the conversion of CO₂ into biofuel or high-added-value biomolecules. The growth and production processes of the biocatalyst will be optimized. Moreover, Polito will optimize the culture media and the possible integration of several processes with each other will be evaluated. The tests will be carried out in laboratory-scale reactors and the products will be characterized according to the techniques already described in the previous tasks. The best solution can be tested on a larger scale.

J) Deliverable D5.2.4

The pursuit of sustainable microalgae production necessitates the development of advanced photobioreactor (PBR) systems that address current limitations in energy efficiency, light management, and process optimization. While microalgae hold great promise as a renewable resource, conventional PBR systems—particularly flat-panel designs—are often hindered by high energy costs and biofouling risks associated with traditional air bubbling methods used for mixing. Moreover, reliance on compressed air significantly contributes to the system's overall energy consumption. This research aims to improve the technological performance and sustainability of PBRs through innovative design and engineering solutions, with a specific focus on enhancing carbon dioxide biofixation by microalgae. We introduce a novel flat-panel PBR equipped with a centrifugal pump-assisted hydraulic circuit designed to mitigate the aforementioned challenges. The system confines microalgae within a pressurized serpentine loop directly exposed to artificial light, optimizing light distribution and improving growth efficiency. The flat panels, just 1.3 cm wide, are specifically engineered to maximize light penetration—an essential factor for photosynthetic activity and biomass accumulation. A schematic of the system is provided in Figure 1. A key innovation of this work is the integration of a tunable LED lighting system composed of 10 discrete LEDs spanning the full PAR (Photosynthetically Active Radiation) range, along with 2 white-light LEDs. This system allows for the customization of light spectra tailored to the specific requirements of different microalgal strains. Such spectral tuning enhances growth by aligning with the algae's photosynthetic responses while also reducing the energy demand for artificial lighting. An example of an optimized spectrum for a selected strain is shown in Figure 2. An in-depth analysis of the fluid dynamics within the novel PBR highlights how the centrifugal pump-assisted hydraulic circuit

influences microalgal circulation and interaction. By optimizing hydrodynamic behavior, the system ensures uniform light exposure, thereby boosting microalgal productivity. The results of fluid dynamic testing are presented in Figures 3 and 4. Achieving a balance between high volumetric productivity and high biomass concentration is critical for efficient PBR operations. To address this, we developed a hybrid modeling approach based on first-principle equations, aimed at streamlining computational efforts and reducing the need for extensive empirical data. The model was trained and validated using batch cultivations of the red microalga *Galdieria sulphuraria*, grown under controlled conditions within the novel PBR. The model demonstrated strong predictive capability, particularly in correlating growth rate with biomass concentration under varying light intensities. These results are illustrated in Figure 5. Furthermore, this study investigates the technical feasibility of water reuse and nutrient recovery specifically for the cultivation of the polyextremophile *G. sulphuraria*. This case study demonstrates how resource-efficient strategies can significantly reduce environmental impact and operating costs in large-scale microalgae production. The results, including a growth curve from a reuse experiment, are shown in Figure 6. In conclusion, this work contributes significantly to the advancement of microalgal biotechnology by presenting a high-efficiency PBR design, a comprehensive analysis of its fluid dynamics, enhanced light management strategies, and a robust hybrid modeling framework for process optimization. The novel flat-panel photobioreactor, featuring a centrifugal pump-assisted hydraulic circuit and customizable LED lighting, offers a promising pathway toward more sustainable and efficient microalgae cultivation. Additionally, this research establishes a foundation for future studies focusing on the refinement and application of hybrid models as engineering tools, while emphasizing the importance of minimizing freshwater consumption to ensure environmental sustainability and optimal resource utilization.

Figure 1: The alveolar flat-panel PBR. A. 3D isometric representation of the PBR. B. Schematic representation of the lighting engine. PLC: Programmable Logic Controller

Figure 2: Light spectra customization. A. Wavelength-specific normalized oxygen evolution response (ΔO_2 [mg L⁻¹] / μE [$\mu\text{molph m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$]) of *A. obliquus*. B. Resultant final spectrum employed for *A. obliquus*. C. Wavelength-specific normalized oxygen evolution response of *G. sulphuraria*. D. Resultant final spectrum employed for *G. sulphuraria*. Graphs were produced with the software OriginPro8.5®.

Figure 3: Visualization of the flow field in the mixing tank, by a contour plot representation of the velocity magnitude field and by fluid path lines. Three cross sections are reported together with a 3D representation.

Figure 4: Visualization of the flow field in the flat panel. A. Velocity magnitude contour plot. B. Fluid path lines. C. Streamlines of the flow field. Each arrow is aligned with the local fluid velocity. The length and colour of the arrows are set according to the velocity magnitude.

Figure 5: Hybrid model derived growth rate (μ) sensitivity with a_x and averaged incident light intensity ($I_{ph}(0)$), assuming a_x stochastic behavior with uniform probability in the range [$\min = 1.4$, $\max = 2.2 \text{ m}^2 \text{ mol}_x^{-1}$]. For each light intensity, it is possible to identify C_x ranges where the

value of αx significantly influences the μ and others where the growth rate is substantially independent of αx .

Figure 6: Biomass concentration over time during cultivation in reused water. Black squares: control (n =3). Orange circles: growth in 98 % reused water from centrifugation (n = 2). Green triangles: growth in 71.5 % reused water from microfiltration.

At the same time, UNITO has worked on the use of enzymes for CO_2 conversion.

This technology aims to enhance efficiency and specificity of the electrochemical reduction of carbon dioxide (CO_2) to formic acid, a high-energy-density liquid compound used for fuel production and as platform chemical, by employing recombinant Clostridial oxygen-tolerant and tungsten dependent Formate Dehydrogenase (FDH) with semiconductor and nanostructured electrodes and photoactivated nanomaterials. The study involves the immobilization of FDH on the electrode surface and optimizing its catalytic performance for formate production. By systematically varying operational conditions and leveraging advanced nanomaterials, we seek to maximize CO_2 conversion efficiency and long-term stability of the bio-hybrid system, while formate production selectivity is already provided by the biocatalyst.

Excellency examples are provided on this bio-hybrid approach by the group of Erwin Reisner at Cambridge University (UK) but on different FDHs and materials. Here we aim at selecting and producing more robust and durable enzymes.

Methodology:

Gene Cloning and Recombinant Expression: The gene encoding Clostridial oxygen-tolerant metal dependent FDH is cloned and inserted into an expression vector for recombinant protein production in *Escherichia coli* hosts. The transformed *E. coli* cells are grown in a suitable culture medium to induce FDH expression. We have already selected and ordered 4 different enzymes form various clostridial strains, yet unexploited, that have the potential oxygen tolerance required for technological applications.

Protein Extraction and Purification: The recombinant FDH is extracted and purified using chromatographic techniques, ensuring high enzyme yield and purity. This is a consolidated expertise of the group and the

expression yields are already in the range of 10-120 mg/l of culture. The enzyme's oxygen tolerance is validated through oxygen sensitivity tests. The possibility of further enhancement of the biocatalyst's performance will be tested by inserting a selenocysteine which is expected to maximize the turnover frequency of the reaction of CO₂ reduction.

Nanomaterial: Different metal oxides nanomaterials, including photo-activated semiconductors and nanostructured electrodes will be available for interfacing with the FDH enzyme. Characterization using scanning electron microscopy (SEM), transmission electron microscopy (TEM), and X-ray diffraction (XRD) is conducted to confirm nanomaterial properties and bio-hybrid structure. This will also be analyzed via ATR FTIR.

Enzyme Immobilization: The extracted FDH is covalently or physically immobilized onto the electrode surface. The optimal FDH loading and immobilization method are determined through systematic experimentation.

Electrochemical Analysis and photoactivation: Electrochemical CO₂ reduction experiments are conducted using the FDH- modified electrodes in a custom-built electrochemical cell. The electrocatalytic performance is monitored by measuring current density, faradaic efficiency, and formate production. Preliminary data were collected on TiO₂ providing gaseous CO₂ which seems to be confirmed as the actual substrate instead of HCO₃⁻].

Optimization: The impact of key operational parameters, including pH, temperature, applied potential and light wavelength and intensity, on CO₂ conversion efficiency and formate yield (quantitated by HPLC analysis of formate) will be studied to identify the optimal conditions.

Expression and purification conditions in E. coli were successfully optimized for all 4 enzymes, however experiments have been mainly carried out on CdFDH and ClFDH.

CdFDH was heterologously expressed in E. coli JM109(DE3) to avoid metal incorporation issues typical of more common strains. Yields of expression ranged from 0.5 - 1.5 mg/l of culture. The incorporation of Tungsten and Iron in the enzyme was qualitatively confirmed by ICP-MS (Inductively Coupled Plasma-Mass Spectrometry).

Activity was assayed spectrophotometrically following NADH consumption under aerobic conditions using bicarbonate as source of carbon dioxide with rates in the 10⁻³ s⁻¹ order of magnitude.

Initial electrochemistry experiments have been conducted immobilizing CdFDH on screen printed ITO electrodes from Metrohm. A catalytic current was detected after the addition of CO₂-saturated buffer; the observed onset potential is consistent with CO₂-to-formate conversion (E₀ = - 420 mV vs SHE). Catalytic currents of 7 microA were recorded on the screen printed electrode, corresponding to current densities of 35.7 microA/cm²

CIFDH was instead exploited for hydrogen-driven CO₂ conversion exploiting a [Fe-Fe]-hydrogenase from *C. beijerinckii* (CbA5H) as shown in the scheme below. The rationale is to exploit [Fe-Fe]-hydrogenases' ability to convert H₂ to protons and electrons (H⁺ + e⁻) with high turnover rates to convert CO₂ to formate with CIFDH. CbA5H was specifically chosen for its ability to withstand O₂ exposure, making it great for industrial applications.

CIFDH was expressed and purified as CdFDH whilst CbA5H was expressed and purified using previously reported conditions .

The two enzymes (1:5 ratio CbA5H:CIFDH) were incubated in H₂-saturated buffer with bicarbonate and formate production was detected. This proof-of-concept system did not require the presence of external electron mediators, paving the way for the direct use of gas mixtures from dark fermentation (H₂:CO₂) as source of electron and CO₂.

The application of recombinant tungsten-dependent Clostridial oxygen-tolerant FDH in *E. coli* for enhanced CO₂ conversion with semiconducting nanomaterials holds great potential for sustainable energy generation and carbon capture. The results achieved: 1) bioelectrocatalysis on ITO up to 35 microA/cm² in current densities and 2) formate production of 200 microM/h in the hydrogen driven two-enzyme system I solution.

K) References

- (1) Carone, M.; Malaguti, M.; Zanetti, M.; Tiraferri, A.; Riggio, V. A. Towards Sustainable Water Management for Galdieria Sulphuraria Cultivation. *Sci. Total Environ.* 2024, 950 (July), 175267. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.175267>.
- (2) Carone, M.; Frungieri, G.; Costamagna, L.; Zanetti, M.; Vanni, M.; Riggio, V. A. Advanced Design and Characterization of a Flat Panel Photobioreactor Equipped with a Customizable Light-Emitting Diode Lighting System. *ACS Sustain. Chem. Eng.* 2024, 12 (7), 2550–2562. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acssuschemeng.3c05176>.
- (3) Miller M, Robinson WE, Oliveira AR, Heidary N, Kornienko N, Warnan J, Pereira IAC, Reisner E.
- (4) Interfacing Formate Dehydrogenase with Metal Oxides for the Reversible Electrocatalysis and Solar-Driven Reduction of Carbon Dioxide. *Angew Chem Int Ed Engl.* 2019 58(14):4601-4605.
- (5) Nielsen, C. F.; Lange, L.; Meyer, A. S. Classification and enzyme kinetics of formate
- (6) dehydrogenases for biomanufacturing via CO₂ utilization. *Biotechnology advances* 2019, 37(7),
- (7) 107408
- (8) Min, K.; Moon, M.; Park, G. W.; Lee, J.; Kim, S. J.; Lee, J. Newly explored formate dehydrogenases from *Clostridium* species catalyze carbon dioxide to formate. *Bioresource Technology* 2022
- (9) Meneghello, M.; Oliveira, A.R.; Jacq-Bailly, A.; Pereira, I.A.C.; Léger, C.; Fourmond, V. Formate
- (10) Dehydrogenases Reduce CO₂ Rather than HCO₃⁻ : An Electrochemical Demonstration. *Angew Chem Int Ed Engl.* 2021 60(18):9964-9967.
- (11) Kuk SK, Gopinath K, Singh RK, Kim TD, Lee Y, Choi WS, et al. NADH-Free Electroenzymatic Reduction of CO₂ by Conductive Hydrogel-Conjugated Formate Dehydrogenase. *ACS Catal.* 2019 Jun 7;9(6):5584–9.
- (12) Morra S, Arizzi M, Valetti F, Gilardi G. Oxygen Stability in the New [FeFe]-Hydrogenase from *Clostridium beijerinckii* SM10 (CbA5H). *Biochemistry.* 2016 Oct 25;55(42):5897–900.

L) Other activities

M) Description of Task 5.2.5 Carbon mineralization.

This task will be led by the Dept. of Earth Sciences (UNITO). Carbon capture through mineralization will be performed via conventional or not-conventional techniques (carbonation,

oxalate precipitation) depending on the characteristics of the system as determined during Task 5.1. The best performing mineralization method will be selected depending on the chemical and physical characteristics of the gases from the emitters. More than one single method will be applied in synergy, if possible, to increase the final performance of the system.

N) Task 5.2.5 Carbon mineralization.

The experimental study focused on CO₂ mineralization processes, particularly exploring carbonation as a “traditional” method. This included investigating its application in the reuse of municipal solid waste (PhD thesis in Earth Sciences by Dr. Quentin Wehrung) and in flue gas treatment through a collaboration with EcoSpray Technologies. The latter involved the formation of metastable carbonate species, such as calcium and magnesium bicarbonates (Master's thesis by Valerio Venezia, in collaboration with Politecnico di Milano and EcoSpray Technologies). The research also involved in-situ spectroscopic analysis to study the kinetics of CO₂ conversion into carbonate ions, and the development of high-efficiency, accelerated carbonation processes through the application of microwave technology to the mineralization system.